

Construction of Ti_3C_2 MXene–semiconductor heterostructures for efficient photocatalytic abatement of sulfamethoxazole[☆]

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ABSTRACT

A series of novel MXene (Ti_3C_2) based photocatalysts designed to obtain an enhance photocatalytic degradation of persistent pollutants have been developed. MXene was used as co-catalyst coupled with different materials. Several materials were prepared to form heterojunctions with MXene, specifically two CaN_4 -based materials and two ZnO-based materials, a bare one and a mixed one with a very low amount of CeO_2 . Sulfamethoxazole (SMZ), a widely used pharmaceutical frequently detected in aqueous systems, was selected as a model contaminant to evaluate the performance of the synthesized materials. MXene–ZnO and MXene–ZnO– CeO_2 heterojunctions were synthesized and characterized to evaluate the structure, the morphology of the systems together with their optical and electronic properties. Photocatalytic tests under simulated solar irradiation showed that MXene–ZnO and MXene–ZnO– CeO_2 composites were the fastest in degrading SMZ, achieving nearly complete SMZ removal within 45 min. The formation of several transformation products was assessed by LC-MS/MS, mainly associated with the S–N cleavage and hydroxylation reactions. Although SMZ was rapidly removed, toxicity prediction (ECOSAR) indicated the formation of intermediates with higher predicted toxicity, requiring longer irradiation times (around 120 min) to achieve effective detoxification.

1. Introduction

Antibiotics are among the most widely consumed classes of drugs worldwide [1] and, due to their widespread use, are frequently detected in various aquatic environments, including surface water, groundwater, and treated wastewater effluents. [1,2] Their environmental persistence, biological activity at very low concentrations, and contribution to induce microbial resistance have raised a growing global concern. [2]

Among these compounds, sulfamethoxazole (SMZ), a sulfonamide antibiotic widely used in veterinary and human medicine to treat bacterial infections, is one of the most frequently detected in the environment, typically at concentrations ranging from ng L^{-1} to $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. [3–7]

Novel degradation approaches have become increasingly necessary, as conventional wastewater treatment methods exhibit significant limitations in removing SMZ. [8–11]

Photocatalysis has emerged as a promising advanced oxidation

process for the degradation of organic pollutants, such as antibiotics. However, its large-scale application remains constrained by challenges related to catalyst efficiency, scalability, and stability under realistic operating conditions. To overcome these limitations, in recent years a novel family of two-dimensional (2D) materials, transition metal carbides, nitrides, and carbonitrides, known as MXenes, has attracted interest. [12–14] MXenes are typically described by the general formula $\text{M}_n\text{X}_n\text{T}_x$, where M denotes a transition metal, X represents carbon and/or nitrogen, and T corresponds to surface terminal groups such as $-\text{O}$, $-\text{OH}$, or $-\text{F}$. Typical MXene structures include $\text{M}_2\text{X}_{t,x}$, $\text{M}_3\text{X}_{2t,x}$, and $\text{M}_4\text{X}_{3t,x}$, offering a wide range of possible compositions and tunable properties [15].

MXenes possess a unique combination of metallic or semi-metallic electrical conductivity, narrow band gaps, large specific surface areas, and abundant surface functional groups, which makes them particularly attractive for photocatalytic systems. In recent years, MXenes have been

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widely explored as co-catalysts in photocatalytic hydrogen evolution reactions (HER), carbon dioxide reduction reactions (CRR), and environmental remediation processes [16]. Compared with noble-metal co-catalysts, MXenes offer advantages in terms of cost, stability, and tunability. When coupled with semiconductor photocatalysts, MXenes effectively suppress the recombination of photogenerated electron-hole pairs and enhance interfacial charge transfer [17].

This enhancement arises primarily from the high work function and excellent electrical conductivity of MXenes. Their Fermi level typically lies below that of common semiconductor photocatalysts, facilitating electron transfer from the semiconductor to the MXene upon photoexcitation. The resulting Fermi-level equilibration leads to the formation of a Schottky barrier at the MXene-semiconductor interface, which prevents electron back-transfer and promotes efficient charge separation. As a result, photogenerated electrons are preferentially trapped within the MXene, while holes remain in the semiconductor, significantly prolonging charge-carrier lifetimes and improving photocatalytic performance. In addition, certain MXenes, most notably $Ti_3C_2T_x$, exhibit localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) effects, which enhance local electromagnetic fields, improve light absorption, and provide additional pathways for charge separation and migration. The high conductivity of MXenes further enables rapid electron transport to reactive surface sites, while their abundant surface terminations offer numerous active sites for catalytic reactions. [16]

MXenes are typically synthesized by selectively etching the “A” element from their corresponding MAX phases using fluoride-based etchants, molten salts (e.g., $CuCl_2$ at elevated temperatures), or alkali-assisted methods. [17–19] Among the various MXene compositions, $Ti_3C_2T_x$ is the most extensively studied due to its exceptional properties, including metallic-like conductivity, high surface area derived from its layered morphology, and rich surface chemistry. [20–22] Importantly, the nature and distribution of surface termination groups can be tailored, allowing fine control over the electronic structure and interfacial interactions of $Ti_3C_2T_x$ -based composites.

Owing to these characteristics, $Ti_3C_2T_x$ has proven to be an effective co-catalyst for constructing semiconductor heterojunctions. It readily forms Schottky-type interfaces with coupled semiconductors, enabling efficient extraction of photoexcited electrons, suppression of charge recombination, and enhancement of photocatalytic activity [23,24].

In this work, we report the design and fabrication of a series of heterojunction photocatalysts composed of Ti_3C_2 MXene, graphitic carbon nitride (g- C_3N_4), and zinc oxide (ZnO) pure and mixed with other oxides), to achieve efficient degradation of the antibiotic sulfamethoxazole (SMZ) under solar-simulated irradiation. Particular attention was devoted to unravel how different synthesis parameters, namely calcination and precipitation, affect the structural, morphological, and photocatalytic properties of the resulting heterojunctions. By systematically comparing these fabrication strategies, this study aims to elucidate the relationship between synthesis conditions, interfacial charge-transfer behavior, and overall photocatalytic performance.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents and materials

Sulfamethoxazole (SMZ, purity grade 99%, Merck), Melamine (99% Merck), Hydrofluoric acid (48%, Merck), Ti_3AlC_2 (MAX phase), zinc acetate dihydrate ($Zn(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, Merck), cerium (III) chloride heptahydrate ($CeCl_3 \cdot 7H_2O$, Merck), NaOH pellets (Merck). Phosphoric acid (H_3PO_4 , 86%, VWR Chemicals).

2.2. Synthesis procedures

2.2.1. MXene synthesis

MXene was synthesized using Ti_3AlC_2 (MAX phase) as the precursor via a conventional chemical etching process with hydrofluoric acid (HF).

[18] Two concentrations were employed to study the effect of etching strength on the final material, respectively HF 5% and 10%.

In a typical synthesis 1.0 g of Ti_3AlC_2 was gradually added to 20 mL of HF 5% and HF 10% solution in a 100 mL Teflon flask, paying attention to the temperature since the reaction is extremely exothermic. The suspension was stirred continuously (500 rpm) for 24 h. Afterward, the suspension was centrifuged at 3500 RPM for 5 min to eliminate the supernatant. The product was washed and centrifuged 3 times with deionized water. After this treatment, the solid was further purified by vacuum filtration with 1 L of deionized water on a cellulose filter. The final solid was dried overnight at 70 °C and subsequently stored for testing and heterojunction fabrication.

2.2.2. Carbon nitride synthesis and MXene heterojunctions fabrication by calcination

Carbon nitride (C_3N_4) was synthesized via thermal polymerization of melamine. [19,20] In a typical procedure, 2 g of melamine was placed in a ceramic crucible, covered with the lid, and heated in a muffle furnace. After cooling, the resulting yellow solid was ground into a fine powder using a mortar and pestle and stored for later use in heterojunction fabrication. Afterwards, two heterojunctions were created by varying the calcination temperature: the two samples were prepared by mixing 250 mg of MXene with 250 mg of C_3N_4 . These mixtures were calcinated at 450 °C and 350 °C, respectively, to investigate the influence of temperature on the structure and phase composition of the resulting MXene- C_3N_4 composites.

2.2.3. Heterojunction formation MXene-ZnO and MXene-ZnO-CeO₂

The fabrication of these two heterojunctions begins by dispersing 0.4 g of MXene in 20 mL of deionized water and subjecting it to sonication for 10 min to achieve a uniform suspension. Then, 2 g of zinc acetate dihydrate ($Zn(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$) was dissolved in a mixture consisting of 160 mL of distilled water and 80 mL of ethanol. For cerium-mixed material, 0.03764 g of cerium (III) chloride heptahydrate ($CeCl_3 \cdot 7H_2O$), corresponding to 1% molar respect to the ZnO amount, was also added. The resulting solution was stirred for 1 h to ensure homogeneity, after which 120 mL of 1 M NaOH solution was added dropwise under continuous stirring to initiate precipitation. The resulting mixture was left to rest for two days, allowing ZnO to precipitate on the MXene surface. The resulting precipitate was collected by filtration and subsequently is dried in an oven and eventually calcined in air at 300 °C for 4 h with heating rate of 5 °C per minute.

2.3. Characterization techniques

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analyses were performed using a PANalytical PW3040/60 X'Pert PRO MPD diffractometer (Malver Panalytical, Almelo, Netherlands) operating at 45 kV and 40 mA, with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.15418$ nm). Scans were conducted in continuous mode over a 2θ range of 5°–60°. Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) was conducted using a TESCAN S9000G (Brno, Czech Republic) to examine the morphology of the MXene and heterojunction particles. Imaging was performed using a working voltage of 10 keV. Elemental distribution of the samples was further investigated using energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) coupled with FESEM. The UV-visible absorption spectra were recorded using a Varian Cary 5 spectrometer, coupled with an integration sphere for diffuse reflectance acquisition, using a Carywin-UV/scan software. A PTFE sample with 100% reflectance was used as the reference. Spectra were registered in the 200–800 nm range at a scan rate of 240 nm/min with a step size of 1 nm. Metal leaching was determined with an Agilent 5110 ICP-OES, Pump speed 12 rpm, RF power 1,2 kW, Nebulizer flow 0,7 L/min, Plasma flow 12,0 L/min, Aux flow 1 L/min. Total organic carbon was measured by a Shimadzu TOC-V CSH analyser equipped with a TNM-1 module and an ASI-V autosampler. The Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) is a Thermo Scientific Tecnai Spirit (BioTwin) at 120 kV. X-

ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analyses were performed using a PHI 5000 VersaProbe II instrument (Physical Electronics, USA) equipped with a monochromatic Al K α radiation source (1486.6 eV). The X-ray beam operated at a power of 24.78 W, and emitted photoelectrons were detected at a take-off angle of 45° relative to the sample surface. During data acquisition, the pressure in the analysis chamber was kept below 10⁻⁵ Pa. Wide-scan (survey) spectra were collected over a binding energy interval of 0–1200 eV with a pass energy of 187.85 eV, whereas high-resolution (HR) spectra were recorded using a lower pass energy of 23.50 eV. Surface charging effects were compensated by a dual-beam charge neutralization system employing low-energy electrons and Ar⁺ ions. The energy scale was referenced to the C 1 s signal of titanium carbide fixed at 281.9 in the pure MXene sample, while C1s at 284.8 eV (C-C/C-H) has been chosen as reference for the remaining samples [21].

Spectral processing and curve fitting were carried out with CasaXPS software (version 2.3.18). A Shirley-type background was applied, and core-level peaks were modelled using mixed Gaussian–Lorentzian functions for oxides components, while LA asymmetric curves have been applied for carbide components. Elemental compositions were determined from the integrated peak areas from HR spectra, applying the sensitivity factors provided by the instrument manufacturer.

Spin-trapping experiments were carried out using a X-band benchtop EPR spectrometer (ADANI's SPINSCAN X). DMPO was employed as spin-trapping molecule and ex situ irradiation experiments to monitor the formation of the radicals were performed using a LED with $\lambda = 365$ nm. The samples were prepared suspending 10 mg of photocatalyst in i) 0.5 mL of DMPO aqueous solution 0.044 M for the hydroxyl radical detection; ii) 0.5 mL of DMPO solution (0.044 M) in acetonitrile, instead of water (to avoid competition with hydroxyl radicals), for the detection of superoxide species.

2.4. Irradiation experiments

The photocatalytic performance of the synthesized materials was tested for the degradation of the SMZ. In a typical experiment, 5 mL of 10 mg L⁻¹ SMZ solution in the presence of 200 ppm of the photocatalyst was introduced into a cylindrical Pyrex glass cell (4.0 cm diameter, 2.4 cm height). The cells were closed with a lateral screw cap and magnetically stirred during irradiation. The experiments were conducted under a Solarbox (CO.FO.ME.GRA., Milan, Italy) irradiation device, equipped with a 1500 W Philips Xenon lamp and a 340 nm cut-off filter, so representing irradiation conditions of a deep-water body, where the short-wave sunlight only reaches the surface layers of the water but does not penetrate most of the water column [22]. After irradiation, 1 mL of the solution was filtered using a 0.45 μ m Millipore Millex-LCR hydrophilic PTFE filters and analyzed via HPLC.

The time trends of SMZ were monitored by HPLC-UV/vis, using a YL9300 HPLC System (Young Lin, S. Korea) equipped with a UV/vis detector, YL9150 Autosampler, and YL-9330 column compartment housing a LichroCART - Lichrospher 100 RP-18 column (Merck, 125 mm \times 4 mm \times 5 μ m). The SMZ was eluted with a mixture composed by 65% of 4.5 mmol L⁻¹ H₃PO₄ in water (A) and 35% acetonitrile (B), with a total flow rate of 1 mL/min and detection at $\lambda = 263$ nm. In these conditions, SMZ eluted at $t_R = 2.8$ min.

For the identification of SMZ transformation products, 1 mL of sample was collected at different irradiation times and analyzed by liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry using a Shimadzu UPLC system coupled to a SCIEX 3200 QTRAP LC-MS/MS instrument (Framingham, MA, USA). Initially, a full scan was acquired in positive Enhanced MS Scan mode, covering a mass range of 50–350 m/z . The ion source parameters were set as follows: curtain gas (CUR) 30 L/min, ion spray floating voltage (ISVF) 4500 V, temperature (TEM) 600 °C, ion source gases (GS1 and GS2) at 20 psi both. The flow rate was set to 0.5 mL/min, using 0.1% formic acid (A) and methanol (B) as mobile phases, using a Kinetex 3.5 μ m PAH column for the chromatographic separation. The gradient program was set as follows: 10% B for the first 10 min,

increased to 100% B within 7 min, rapidly returned to 10% B in 0.1 min, and maintained at this level until the end of the 25 min run. The declustering potential (DP) was 20 V, collision energy (CE) was 10 eV, and the entrance potential was set to 10 V. The acquisition of MS/MS data was performed using enhanced product ion scan (EPI) with the following parameters: curtain gas (CUR) 35 L/min, ion spray floating voltage (ISVF) 4500 V, temperature (TEM) 450 °C; ion source gases (GS1 and GS2) 45 psi and 55 psi, respectively. The collision energy (CE) was 10 eV, the declustering potential (DP) was 20 V, and the entrance potential was set to 10 V.

2.5. Toxicity assessments

The toxicity of SMZ and its TPs were predicted using the Ecological Structure Activity Relationships (ECOSAR) predictive model (version 2.2) [23]. The assessment focused on the worst-case toxicity scenario. ECOSAR offers three endpoints: (i) LC₅₀, the concentration lethal to 50% of test organisms; (ii) EC₅₀, the concentration at which 50% of organisms show a specific effect, for example growth inhibition; and (iii) the Chronic Value (ChV), calculated as the geometric mean of NOEC and LOEC. These values (mg L⁻¹) were predicted for fish (LC₅₀, ChV), daphnids (LC₅₀, ChV), and green algae (EC₅₀, ChV), representing three trophic levels commonly used in aquatic toxicity testing. Lower values indicate higher toxicity. The use of these model organisms is consistent with OECD guidelines and regulatory frameworks, which recommend them for risk assessment of contaminants and their transformation products [23,24].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structural characterization

To verify the successful synthesis, X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD) analysis was performed on two MXene samples prepared using 5% and 10% hydrofluoric acid (HF), respectively. Fig. 1a presents a comparison between the parent MAX phase (Ti₃AlC₂) and the two exfoliated MXene samples. HF is used to selectively etching the A layer from the MAX phase that correspond to Al element. This reaction produces multilayered MXene sheets with thanks to the removal of Al.

The MAX phase displays its most intense characteristic peaks at 9.8° and 38.9°, corresponding to the (002) and (104) crystallographic planes according to the JCPDS card No. 52e0875 [25]. Following exfoliation with 5% and 10% HF, new peaks emerge at 9.2°, 18.7°, and 28.1°, which are typical of MXene structures [26–28], nevertheless the etching process produced single-layer flakes that are still loosely held together with van der Waals forces but the bonding between the layers is decreased and thus the distance between layers increased. The sample synthesized with 10% HF exhibits a clean XRD pattern without impurities, indicating effective etching and exfoliation. In contrast, the 5% HF sample shows residual peaks from the MAX phase, the persistence of the peak at 38.9° and the presence of overlapping peaks near 9°, suggesting incomplete conversion and coexistence of MXene (9.2°) and MAX phase (9.8°). In Fig. 1a XRD patterns of the MXene-C₃N₄ heterojunctions calcinated at two different temperature (350 and 450 °C) are reported and compared with the MXene 5% used for their production. A common feature across the calcinated samples is the presence of traces of TiO₂, formed in situ due to the partial oxidation of MXene during calcination. Notably, as the calcination temperature increases, the intensity of TiO₂ peaks increases, indicating higher content of crystalline titania. Nevertheless, the presence of MXene is still confirmed in all the samples by the characteristic peak at 9.2°. In the sample calcined at 450 °C it is possible to observe a small peak at 27.6° (002) due to the presence of C₃N₄ while in the sample calcined at 350 °C the peak of C₃N₄ is much higher due to the lower concentration of titania in the sample. These results confirm the successful preparation of the C₃N₄-MXene. Fig. 1c presents the XRD patterns of two additional heterojunctions based on MXene-ZnO and

Fig. 1. XRD analysis of the tested samples, respectively: (a) Comparison between the pristine MAX phase and the synthesized MXene; (b) comparison among MXene 5%, MXene C₃N₄ 350 °C and MXene C₃N₄ 450 °C; (c) MXene-ZnO composite, cerium oxide-doped MXene-ZnO-CeO₂ composite and MXene 10%.

MXene-ZnO mixed with Cerium oxide (MXene-ZnO-CeO₂), both compared with the MXene 10% which was used to produce these two heterojunctions. Both MXene-ZnO samples display the typical diffraction peaks of ZnO, along with low signals corresponding to MXene, confirming the coexistence of both phases. In the case of the Ce oxide composite, a weak additional peak at 28.9° is observed, which can be attributed to the presence of CeO₂. Other than this minor difference, the presence of CeO₂ does not modify the XRD pattern compared to the pure ZnO as already described and demonstrated in a previous work of E. Cerrato et al. [29]

3.2. Morphology characterization

A crucial aspect in the characterization of this class of 2D materials is the analysis of their morphology. To visualize the surface features of the synthesized samples, Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FESEM) was employed. Fig. 2 presents four representative samples: the two pristine MXene materials synthesized using hydrofluoric acid (HF) at concentrations of 5% and 10%, and two heterojunction systems, namely MXene-C₃N₄ calcined at 450 °C and MXene-ZnO-CeO₂.

As shown in Fig. 2a, the MXene sample synthesized with 5% HF exhibits the characteristic “accordion-like” morphology typical of MXene structures [30,31], clearly displaying the 2D layered arrangement. In Fig. SM1 the elemental quantification of MXene obtained via etching with 5% HF has been reported in which it is evident the presence of Al even after the etching process. Moreover, also XRD analysis revealed the presence of residual MAX phase in this sample, a

comparative morphological investigation between the samples synthesized with 5% HF and 10% HF was conducted. The FESEM image of the MXene prepared using 10% HF (Fig. 2c) also shows the typical accordion-like structure, analogous to that of the 5% HF sample, with no significant morphological differences observed. This suggests that the residual MAX phase detected by XRD cannot be distinguished at the morphological level, confirming the successful synthesis of MXene in both cases.

In contrast, distinct morphological differences are evident between the two heterojunction systems. In Fig. 2b, the MXene-C₃N₄ sample calcined at 450 °C retains the characteristic 2D layered structure of MXene, despite the partial oxidation of Ti₃C₂ to TiO₂ during calcination (evidences of the presence of TiO₂ could be observed also in Fig. SM2 while in the case of sample calcined at 350 °C the atomic % of oxygen is much lower as reported in Fig. SM3). Conversely, as shown in Fig. 2d, the MXene-ZnO-CeO₂ composite exhibits a surface completely covered by ZnO-CeO₂ particles, which obscure the underlying accordion-like morphology. This complete coverage is attributed to the precipitation synthesis method, which promotes uniform deposition of the oxide particles across the MXene surface. On the contrary C₃N₄ presumably forms thin layers on MXene surface so the morphological aspect of the MXene is not completely covered and could be preserved even in the mixed samples (other details of the elemental analysis and maps can be seen in Figs. SM4-SM9). Further analysis with Transmission Electron Microscope has been performed and images in diffraction and transmission mode have been registered (Fig. SM10-SM12).

Fig. 2. FESEM pictures of the following materials: a) MXene synthesized by HF 5%, b) MXene-C₃N₄ 450 °C, c) MXene synthesized by HF 10%, d) MXene-ZnO-CeO₂.

Fig. 3. UV-Vis spectra of a) pristine MXene, C₃N₄, MXene-C₃N₄ 350 °C and MXene-C₃N₄ 450 °C, b) pristine MXene, pure ZnO, MXene-ZnO and MXene-ZnO-CeO₂.

3.3. Optical and electronic characterization

The optical properties of the synthesized samples were studied using UV–Vis diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS) to analyze the materials light absorption. The following figure (Fig. 3) presents the UV–Vis spectra of the pure MXene, of the heterojunctions of MXene-ZnO and MXene-ZnO-CeO₂, both prepared using precipitation method; MXene-C₃N₄ 350 °C, MXene-C₃N₄ 450 °C prepared using calcination method at the respective temperatures.

From the UV–Vis absorption spectra distinct optical behaviors are evident between the samples synthesized via C₃N₄ incorporation and those prepared through ZnO precipitation. The two ZnO-based heterojunctions exhibit nearly identical absorption profiles, both showing an absorption onset around 400 nm. The only noticeable difference appears in the 500–800 nm region, where the MXene-ZnO-CeO₂ sample displays slightly enhanced absorption relative to MXene-ZnO, suggesting an extended photo-response into the visible range.

In contrast, the MXene-C₃N₄ composites (Fig. 3a) show an absorption onset at approximately 450 nm, primarily attributed to the intrinsic absorption of C₃N₄. Furthermore, a clear dependence on calcination temperature is observed: the MXene-C₃N₄ sample treated at 450 °C exhibits a markedly stronger overall absorption compared to the one calcined at 350 °C, indicating improved light-harvesting capability at higher calcination temperatures.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was used to probe the surface chemistry and electronic properties of the MXene-based composites. In particular, core-level spectra were analyzed to identify the chemical states of the elements, while valence band measurements were exploited to gain insight into the electronic structure and interfacial charge redistribution in the different heterostructures.

The survey spectra of all samples (Fig. 4) confirm the successful incorporation of the secondary phases on the MXene surface. In addition to Ti, C, O and F from the MXene, the MXene-C₃N₄ sample shows intense N signals, while the MXene-ZnO-CeO_x composite exhibits clear Zn, while Ce contribution cannot be clearly seen. Only in the pure MXene sample and in the MXenes with C₃N₄ residual amounts of Al, coming from the MAX phase, have been detected (see Table 1).

The relative atomic concentrations, reported in Table 1 and derived

Table 1

XPS relative atomic concentrations (at.%) calculated from HR spectra.

SAMPLE	Atomic concentration [at.%]							
	C1s	O1s	Ti2p	F1s	Al2s	N1s	Zn2p3	Ce3d
1-MXene	38.4	34.2	18.4	7.5	1.5	/	/	/
2- MXene-C ₃ N ₄ @450 °C	29.6	30.3	11.5	3.1	2.0	23.5	/	/
3- MXene-C ₃ N ₄ @350 °C	46.0	15.3	3.9	1.6	0.7	32.6	/	/
4- MXene-ZnO- CeO _x	25.3	51.1	1.9	/	/	/	21.2	0.5

from high-resolution core-level spectra, indicate a surface strongly enriched in O, N and Zn, reflecting both the high surface reactivity of the MXene and the covering due to C₃N₄ and ZnO-CeO₂, as previously confirmed by SEM analysis. The significant O content suggests partial surface oxidation of the MXene sheets, which is commonly observed for Ti₃C₂T_x exposed to air or aqueous environments [32].

The signal from the Ti2p region (see Fig. 5) corresponding to the pure MXene sample presents a rather complex structure to analyze. This behavior is very common in the literature and is due to the large surface area of the material, its high reactivity, and the presence of surface passivation resulting from both oxidation and residues from the chemical exfoliation treatment of the MAX phase, which left a functionalization with residual F, and Al atoms that has not been completely eliminated with HF treatment. As reported in the detailed study by F. Brette et al. [21], it is also necessary to take into account not only the chemical environment of the atoms present on the surface (“surface atoms”), but also those present in the volume (“bulk atoms”) that the technique is able to probe. At the same time, the morphology of the bonds formed, i.e., the interatomic distances due to the length of the bonds involved, also play a fundamental role in the creation of “chemical shifts,” often misunderstood in the literature. In this regard, the bonds present on the surface are much more sensitive to interatomic distances and the presence of oxidation, leading to a shift for the Ti_xC_y component of about 1.52 eV, going from 453.7 eV for Ti₃C₂ to 455.2 eV for Ti₃C₂O₂. Taking this work as a reference, together with [33,34], we assigned the peaks obtained by deconvolution of the Ti2p region of pure

Fig. 4. XPS survey spectra (from top to bottom) of pure MXene, MXene-C₃N₄ 450 °C, MXene-C₃N₄ 350 °C and MXene-ZnO-CeO₂.

Fig. 5. XPS Ti2p HR spectra for (from top to bottom in clockwise order): MXene, MXene- C₃N₄ 450 °C, MXene- C₃N₄ 350 °C and MXene-ZnO-CeO₂.

MXene, to the following contributions: 455.1 eV to Ti–C (MXene), 456.4 to Ti₃C₂O₂, 457.7 eV to Ti_xO_y, 459.6 eV to TiO_{2-x}F_{2-x} and 460.9 eV to Ti-C-F surface species.

In all investigated composite samples, the Ti 2p spectra are dominated by Ti³⁺/Ti⁴⁺ components in the 457–459 eV range, while the characteristic carbide-related Ti–C signal at ~455 eV is strongly

suppressed or not detectable. This indicates that, independently of the secondary phase, the MXene surface is largely converted into TiO_x, leading to a Ti₃C₂@TiO_x core–shell structure.

As with the Ti2p region, the HR region of the C1s (Fig. 6) also shows a much more complex structure in the pure MXene sample, compared to those of the composites. Starting from the components with the lowest

Fig. 6. XPS C1s HR spectra for (from top to bottom in clockwise order): MXene, MXene- C₃N₄ 450 °C, MXene- C₃N₄ 350 °C and MXene-ZnO-CeO₂.

binding energy, the MXene “fingerprint” peak is located at 281.9 eV. Next to it (282.4 eV) is the peak due to the F-terminations present on the MXene surface (C-Ti-Tx), and then at 283.4 eV the peak due to the presence of the passivated MXene surface (C-Ti-Ox). At around 285 eV, the component due to adventitious C contamination is present, while at 286.7 eV the large contribution due to the C-OH/C-O terminations is noted, followed by the last two components at 289.0 and 290.8 eV, due to C=O and O-C=O, respectively [35].

The C 1 s spectrum of the MXene-C₃N₄ samples shows multiple components associated with different carbon chemical environments. The dominant peak at ~288.2 eV is assigned to sp²-hybridized carbon in N-C=N units, which represents the fingerprint of the C₃N₄ framework, together with the p-p* shake up feature at 294 eV. Additional contributions at ~284.8 eV and ~286 eV are attributed to adventitious carbon (C-C/C=C) and surface C-N/C-O species, respectively. In contrast, the carbide-related C-Ti signal expected at ~281.8–282.0 eV is either very weak or not clearly distinguishable, consistently with the strong surface oxidation of the MXene evidenced by the Ti 2p spectrum. In contrast, the MXene-ZnO-CeO_x composite does not show this features, and the C 1 s region is mainly composed of adventitious carbon and surface C-O species, as expected for an oxide-based system.

The Zn2p spectrum of the MXene-ZnO-CeO_x composite (see Fig. 7) shows a well-defined Zn 2p_{3/2} peak at 1021.4 eV, which is characteristic of Zn²⁺ in doped ZnO [36]. No additional components related to metallic Zn or hydroxide species are detected, indicating that zinc is present exclusively in the oxide form. The Ce3d HR spectrum of the MXene-ZnO-CeO_x composite exhibits only the characteristic features of Ce³⁺ species, with no detectable contributions from Ce⁴⁺, especially the peak usually located at ~916 eV, which is Ce⁴⁺ finger print [37]. This indicates that cerium is present at the surface exclusively in a reduced oxidation state, corresponding to a Ce₂O₃-like phase. (See Fig. 8.)

The dominance of Ce³⁺ implies a high concentration of oxygen vacancies, which are known to act as electron donors and to strongly enhance interfacial charge transfer processes.

The valence band spectra (Fig. 5) reveal a clear evolution of the electronic structure upon formation of the heterostructures. Pristine MXene exhibits a VBM of (1.10 ± 0.01) eV, indicating a quasi-metallic behavior dominated by TiO_x-derived states near the Fermi level [38].

In contrast, both MXene-C₃N₄ composites display significantly higher VBM values (2.34 ± 0.01 eV for 350 °C and 2.51 ± 0.01 eV for 450 °C), reflecting the semiconducting nature of C₃N₄ and the progressive strengthening of the electronic coupling with increasing annealing temperature [39].

The MXene-ZnO-CeO₂ composite shows the highest VBM (2.61 ± 0.01 eV), indicating a deeper valence band edge associated with the combined contribution of ZnO band states and Ce³⁺-related defect levels [40]. The presence of exclusively Ce³⁺ species suggests a high density of

oxygen vacancies, which introduce electronic states near the band edges and promote strong interfacial charge transfer.

The superior photocatalytic performance of the MXene-ZnO-CeO_x composite can be directly correlated with its electronic structure. The deeper valence band position and the exclusive presence of Ce³⁺ species indicate a high density of oxygen vacancies and defect states, which act as efficient charge trapping and transfer centres. These features strongly suppress electron-hole recombination and promote interfacial charge separation, resulting in enhanced generation of reactive species and improved photocatalytic degradation efficiency. While the MXene-C₃N₄ heterostructure benefits from band alignment-driven charge separation, the MXene-ZnO-CeO_x system exhibits an additional defect-mediated charge transfer mechanism associated with Ce³⁺-induced oxygen vacancies, which provides a more efficient pathway for photogenerated charge utilization.

Overall, the valence band analysis demonstrates that while pristine MXene retains a quasi-metallic character, both heterostructures behave as true semiconducting systems. However, the electronic structure of MXene-ZnO-CeO₂ is dominated by defect-mediated states associated with Ce³⁺-induced oxygen vacancies, leading to a deeper valence band and a fundamentally different charge transfer mechanism compared to MXene-C₃N₄.

3.4. Sulfamethoxazole photocatalytic degradation

Prior to the photocatalytic tests, control experiments were performed to assess the contribution of direct photolysis on SMZ removal and the extent of adsorption in the dark in the presence of the investigated materials [41]. In both cases, SMZ removal was negligible, as shown in Fig. SM13. The photocatalytic performances of all the synthesized materials for the degradation of SMZ under simulated solar irradiation are shown in Fig. 9, and pseudo-first-order rate constants (k') are collected in Table 2.

The photocatalytic efficiency follows the order: MXene-ZnO-CeO₂ > MXene-ZnO >> MXene-C₃N₄ 450 °C > MXene-C₃N₄ 350 °C > MXene 5% HF > MXene 10% HF. Pristine MXene samples exhibited negligible SMZ degradation over 2 h, indicating that MXene does not act as an efficient standalone photocatalyst under the applied conditions. Instead, its primary function is that of a **conductive substrate and co-catalyst**, which becomes catalytically active only when coupled with a photoactive semiconductor through heterojunction formation. The MXene-C₃N₄ composites exhibited moderate photocatalytic activity, with comparable half-lives of approximately 2 h for both calcination temperatures. The slightly higher activity observed for the sample calcined at 350 °C can be attributed to improved interfacial contact and preserved surface functional groups. However, the overall degradation efficiency remains limited, suggesting sub-optimal charge-separation pathways in this system. Even if it has been demonstrated the formation of titania, generated by the oxidation of MXene phase during the calcination process, it does not affect the photocatalytic activity of the samples that is not so intense.

In contrast, the introduction of ZnO leads to a dramatic enhancement of photocatalytic performance. Both MXene-ZnO and MXene-ZnO-CeO₂ systems achieve complete SMZ degradation within 1 h, with the Ce-containing composite exhibiting the highest reaction rate. This improvement can be rationalized by considering the **electronic structure alignment and interfacial charge-transfer processes** within these heterojunctions.

XRD patterns reveal that crystalline ZnO dominates the composite structure, while FESEM images confirm that ZnO particles are uniformly distributed over and partially encapsulate the accordion-like MXene layers. This intimate interfacial contact is essential for efficient charge transport across the heterojunction. UV-Vis diffuse reflectance spectra further show that ZnO-containing samples exhibit enhanced absorption extending into the visible region, which is attributed to **plasmonic-type interactions and electronic coupling between ZnO and MXene**.

Fig. 7. XPS Zn2p (left) and Ce3d (right) HR spectra for MXene-ZnO-CeO₂ sample.

Fig. 8. XPS Valence band regions spectra (from top to bottom) of pure MXene, MXene- C_3N_4 450 °C, MXene- C_3N_4 350 °C and MXene-ZnO-CeO₂. Valence Band Maximum (VBM) values have been reported, together with the reference Fermi level (E_F) at 0.0 eV.

Fig. 9. Photodegradation time trends of 10 ppm SMZ solution in the presence of 200 ppm photocatalyst upon irradiation under the solar simulator equipped with a 340 nm cut-off filter.

Table 2

Pseudo-first order rate constants (k') for SMZ in the presence of different photocatalysts under solar-simulated irradiation.*

Photocatalyst (200 mg L ⁻¹)	SMZ, k' (h ⁻¹)
MXene- C_3N_4 450 °C	0.269 ± 0.028
MXene- C_3N_4 350 °C	0.305 ± 0.025
MXene HF 10%	–
MXene HF 5%	0.171 ± 0.067
MXene -ZnO	4.833 ± 0.148
MXene -ZnO-Ce	5.741 ± 0.184

* n.d. = not determined due to negligible degradation.

Upon solar irradiation, ZnO acts as the primary photoactive component,

generating electron-hole pairs. Due to the lower Fermi level and high electrical conductivity of MXene, photogenerated electrons in the conduction band of ZnO are rapidly transferred to the MXene surface. This electron migration is driven by Fermi-level equilibration and results in the formation of a **Schottky barrier at the MXene-ZnO interface**, which effectively suppresses electron back-transfer and recombination. Consequently, photogenerated holes remain in the ZnO valence band, where they can participate in oxidation reactions leading to SMZ degradation, while electrons accumulated on MXene facilitate reduction reactions involving dissolved oxygen, generating reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as $O_2^{\bullet-}$ [42]. To demonstrate this process, we performed spin trapping experiments through EPR analysis. DMPO was employed as spin-trapping molecule and ex situ irradiation experiments to monitor the formation of the radicals were performed using a LED with $\lambda = 365$ nm.

The role of MXene in this system is therefore twofold:

- it serves as an **electron sink and conductive highway**, accelerating charge separation and transport;
- it provides abundant surface sites that promote interfacial redox reactions.

The presence of Ce further enhances this process by introducing oxygen vacancies and defect states that improve charge trapping and ROS generation, accounting for the superior activity of the MXene-ZnO-CeO₂ composite. The MXene-ZnO system is particularly reactive toward the formation of OH^{\bullet} radicals, whereas the system also containing cerium oxide shows higher reactivity in the production of superoxide anions ($O_2^{\bullet-}$). This behavior can be explained by the tendency of cerium to undergo reduction to Ce^{3+} , which acts as an electron reservoir and is therefore more suitable for promoting reduction reactions.

In the MXene- C_3N_4 system, a different charge-transfer pathway is proposed. Due to the relative band positions of C_3N_4 and MXene, photogenerated electrons tend to remain in the conduction band of C_3N_4 , while holes are partially neutralized by electrons transferred from MXene. This recombination pathway limits hole-driven oxidation

reactions, resulting in lower SMZ degradation efficiency compared to ZnO-based systems. Consequently, this heterojunction configuration favors reduction reactions over oxidative degradation, explaining its inferior photocatalytic performance.

Based on these observations in agreement with reported literature [16,38], and on the XPS results reported above the enhanced photocatalytic performance of the MXene–ZnO–CeO_x composite is closely linked to its electronic structure. The deeper valence band maximum and the exclusive presence of Ce³⁺ species suggest a high concentration of oxygen vacancies and defect-related states, which serve as effective charge trapping and transfer centers. These characteristics markedly suppress electron–hole recombination and facilitate interfacial charge separation, thereby promoting the generation of reactive species and improving photocatalytic degradation efficiency.

Although the MXene–C₃N₄ heterostructure primarily relies on band alignment to drive charge separation, the MXene–ZnO–CeO_x system benefits from an additional defect-mediated charge transfer pathway associated with Ce³⁺-induced oxygen vacancies. This mechanism provides a more efficient route for the utilization of photogenerated charge carriers.

Overall, valence band analysis reveals that while pristine MXene maintains a quasi-metallic character, both heterostructures exhibit semiconducting behavior. Nevertheless, the electronic structure of MXene–ZnO–CeO_x is predominantly governed by defect-induced states arising from Ce³⁺-related oxygen vacancies, resulting in a deeper valence band and a fundamentally distinct charge transfer mechanism compared to MXene–C₃N₄.

A qualitative comparison with previously reported MXene-based systems (Table 3) shows that the present catalysts achieve competitive degradation efficiencies under environmentally relevant solar-simulated irradiation conditions. Owing to differences in light sources, irradiance, and experimental setups, the comparison is intended to be indicative rather than strictly quantitative.

Table 3 reports other MXene-based photocatalysts from the literature used for the degradation of sulfamethoxazole, allowing a direct comparison with our results.

3.5. Reusability and metal stability

The operational stability of MXene–ZnO–CeO₂ was evaluated over four consecutive photocatalytic cycles under identical conditions (Fig. SM14). After each run, the catalyst was recovered, washed, dried, and reused. No significant loss in SMZ degradation efficiency was observed, confirming excellent recyclability.

Metal leaching was quantified after the fourth cycle. Ce concentration in solution was below the detection limit of the analytical technique used, indicating well retention of cerium within the composite structure. Zn release corresponded to approximately 0.5% of the total Zn content after four cycles, which can be considered negligible, so proving the structural robustness of the MXene–oxide heterostructures under simulated solar irradiation.

3.6. Photo-transformation products and toxicity assessment

The formation of transformation products (TPs) during SMZ

photodegradation was also evaluated for the two best-performing photocatalysts, namely MXene–ZnO and MXene–ZnO–Ce. Under these conditions, two main TPs were identified (Table 4). The products were identified using LC-MS/MS based on their *m/z* ratios, MS/MS fragmentation patterns from databases (MassBank, <https://massbank.eu/MassBank/>), and literature findings.

The fragmentation pathways for SMZ and the identified TPs are presented in Fig. SM15. TP1 (*m/z* 255) is attributed to the hydroxylation of the parent molecule, consistent with substitution of the amino group. The production at *m/z* 161, formed via the cleavage of the C–S bond on the phenolic moiety, in addition to the ions at *m/z* 157 and *m/z* 99 resulting from the rupture of the S–N bond, supports this structural attribution (see Fig. SM15 b).

This TP has also been observed in previous studies using different photocatalysts, such as g-C₃N₄/Bi₂WO₆/MoS₂ and N,S-doped TiO₂@C derived from Ti₃C₂ MXene [46,47], whose formation is mainly driven by reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as OH[•] and O₂^{•-} [48]. These species promote common reactions, including hydroxylation and S–N bond cleavage, yielding to this frequently detected TP [48].

TP2 (*m/z* 99), can be formed through the S–N bond cleavage, with the formation of the product ion at *m/z* 72 formed by the elimination of a -CHN group (see Fig. SM15 c). The formation of this TP under photocatalytic conditions was also observed in previous studies [48–50].

The temporal evolution of the detected TPs (Fig. SM16) shows that TP1 reaches its maximum yield after 45 min of irradiation and completely disappears within 120 min. TP2 follows a similar trend, with the maximum at around 30 min and the complete removal achieved within 120 min. At that time (120 min), a significant extent of mineralization was achieved (80% in the case of MXene–ZnO–Ce and 68% in the case of MXene–ZnO).

These findings highlight that rapid SMZ disappearance does not necessarily correspond to immediate detoxification. Table 5 presents the ECOSAR-predicted toxicity values for SMZ and its transformation products toward key species, including fish, daphnids, and green algae. This ECOSAR screening indicates that TP1 exhibits lower predicted LC₅₀, EC₅₀, and chronic values compared to SMZ, suggesting higher potential ecotoxicity, particularly toward daphnids, which appear as the most sensitive species. TP2 exhibits intermediate predicted toxicity, greater than SMZ but generally lower than TP1.

According to the literature, TP1 would be classified as toxic, whereas SMZ and TP2 is categorized as not-harmful [51,52]. Although ECOSAR predicted higher toxicity for TP2 compared with SMZ, no adverse effects were observed in growth inhibition assays with *Vibrio fischeri* [53]. This suggests that the conditions that favor the formation of TP1 could have relevant ecological implications, especially for fish and algae (Fig. SM16).

4. Conclusion

In this work, Ti₃C₂ MXene-based heterostructures were rationally engineered and systematically compared to elucidate how interfacial design and electronic structure govern photocatalytic performance toward sulfamethoxazole (SMZ) degradation under solar-simulated irradiation.

While pristine MXene exhibited negligible activity, its role as a

Table 3
MXene-based photocatalysts for the degradation of sulfamethoxazole.

Ref	Paper	Photocatalyst (g L ⁻¹)	SMZ (mg L ⁻¹)	Irradiation Source	Irradiance	Time (min)	Degradation (%)
[43]	In ₂ S ₃ /Ti ₃ C ₂ MXene QD/SmFeO ₃	0.6	10	Xenon lamp	n.r.	90	95.4
[44]	Bi ₂ O ₃ /C ₃ N ₄ /TiO ₂ @C	1.0	5	Xenon lamp λ > 420 nm	250 mW/cm ²	100	100
[45]	MXene-Derived Oxide	0.20	13	UVA 335–380 nm	1.5 W/cm ²	120	83.0
This work	MXene–ZnO–Ce	0.20	10	Xenon lamp	19 W/m ² (UV region)	45	99.8

n.r. = not reported.

Table 4
Identified TPs of SMZ using different photo-catalyzers.

Compound	Elemental composition	[M + H] ⁺	MS/MS product ions	Relative abundance (%)	Structure
SMZ	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₃ S	254	156 108 92	90 91 100	
TP1	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄ S	255	161 157 99	21 100 81	
TP2	C ₄ H ₆ N ₂ O	99	72	21	

Table 5
ECOSAR-predicted acute (LC₅₀, EC₅₀) and chronic (ChV) toxicity values for SMZ and its transformation products.

Compound	Organism	Duration (h)	End Point	
			LC ₅₀ or EC ₅₀ (mg L ⁻¹)	ChV (mg L ⁻¹)
SMZ	Fish	96	2.67 × 10 ²	5
	Daphnid	48	6.43	6.82 × 10 ⁻²
	Green Algae	96	21.8	11.1
	Algae			
TP1	Fish	96	13.5	1.25 × 10 ⁻¹
	Daphnid	48	1.09	2.28 × 10 ⁻¹
	Green Algae	96	2.20	3.7 × 10 ⁻¹
	Algae			
TP2	Fish	96	2.70 × 10 ²	6.59
	Daphnid	48	3.63	3.63 × 10 ⁻²
	Green Algae	96	13.9	9.16
	Algae			

conductive co-catalyst became evident upon coupling with semiconductor phases. Among the investigated systems, ZnO-based heterostructures dramatically outperformed the C₃N₄ counterparts, with the MXene–ZnO–CeO_x composite achieving nearly complete SMZ removal within 45 min and the highest kinetic constant ($k' = 5.741 \text{ h}^{-1}$). The catalyst also demonstrated excellent structural robustness, recyclability, and negligible metal leaching, confirming its stability under operational conditions.

Comprehensive structural and electronic characterization revealed that the superior activity of MXene–ZnO–CeO_x originates from a synergistic combination of Schottky-driven charge separation and defect-mediated charge transfer. XPS valence band analysis demonstrated a progressive evolution from quasi-metallic MXene to semiconducting heterostructures, with the ZnO–CeO_x system exhibiting the deepest valence band maximum. The exclusive presence of Ce³⁺ species indicates a high concentration of oxygen vacancies, which introduce defect states that act as electron reservoirs and promote interfacial charge migration. This defect-assisted pathway provides a fundamentally different and more efficient charge utilization mechanism compared to the band-alignment-driven process operating in MXene–C₃N₄ systems.

Importantly, this study highlights that rapid disappearance of the parent pollutant does not necessarily imply detoxification. Although SMZ was efficiently removed, transformation products with higher predicted ecotoxicity were transiently formed, requiring extended irradiation times to achieve effective detoxification and mineralization. This finding underscores the importance of integrating degradation kinetics with toxicity assessment in photocatalytic water treatment studies.

Overall, this work demonstrates that defect engineering at MXene–semiconductor interfaces represents a powerful strategy to enhance photocatalytic efficiency. In particular, the incorporation of low amounts of CeO_x enables the transition from a conventional Schottky heterojunction to a defect-dominated charge-transfer system, opening new avenues for the rational design of MXene-based photocatalysts for environmental remediation.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Paolo Iaconis: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Manuel A. Andino Enriquez:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Fhebe Lagaac Angus:** Investigation, Data curation. **Vittorio Boffa:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Micaela Castellino:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Maria Cristina Paganini:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: “Given her role as editor, Paola Calza had no involvement in the peer review of this article and had no access to information regarding its peer review. Full responsibility for the editorial process for this article was delegated to another journal editor.”

If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2026.175924>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] S. Manzetti, R. Ghisi, The environmental release and fate of antibiotics, *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 79 (2014) 7–15, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2014.01.005>.
- [2] S.I. Polianciuc, A.E. Gurzau, B. Kiss, M. Georgia Ștefan, F. Loghin, Antibiotics in the environment: causes and consequences, *Med. Pharm. Rep.* 93 (2020) 231–240, <https://doi.org/10.15386/mpr-1742>.
- [3] L. Du, W. Liu, Occurrence, fate, and ecotoxicity of antibiotics in agro-ecosystems. A review, *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 32 (2012) 309–327, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-011-0062-9>.
- [4] R. Zhang, J. Tang, J. Li, Z. Cheng, C. Chaemfa, D. Liu, Q. Zheng, M. Song, C. Luo, G. Zhang, Occurrence and risks of antibiotics in the coastal aquatic environment of the Yellow Sea, North China, *Sci. Total Environ.* 450–451 (2013) 197–204, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2013.02.024>.
- [5] F. Santos, C.M.R. de Almeida, I. Ribeiro, A.C. Ferreira, A.P. Mucha, Removal of veterinary antibiotics in constructed wetland microcosms – Response of bacterial communities, *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 169 (2019) 894–901, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2018.11.078>.
- [6] P.J.M. Reis, V. Homem, A. Alves, V.J.P. Vilar, C.M. Manaia, O.C. Nunes, Insights on sulfamethoxazole bio-transformation by environmental Proteobacteria isolates, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 358 (2018) 310–318, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2018.07.012>.
- [7] S. Prasertkulsak, C. Chiemchaisri, W. Chiemchaisri, T. Itonaga, K. Yamamoto, Removals of pharmaceutical compounds from hospital wastewater in membrane bioreactor operated under short hydraulic retention time, *Chemosphere* 150 (2016) 624–631, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2016.01.031>.
- [8] J. Wang, S. Wang, Microbial degradation of sulfamethoxazole in the environment, *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 102 (2018) 3573–3582, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-018-8845-4>.
- [9] P.J.M. Reis, A.C. Reis, B. Ricken, B.A. Kolvenbach, C.M. Manaia, P.F.X. Corvini, O. C. Nunes, Biodegradation of sulfamethoxazole and other sulfonamides by *Achromobacter denitrificans* P1, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 280 (2014) 741–749, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2014.08.039>.
- [10] G. Zhu, Q. Sun, C. Wang, Z. Yang, Q. Xue, Removal of sulfamethoxazole, sulfathiazole and sulfamethazine in their mixed solution by UV/H₂O₂ process, *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 16 (2019), <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16101797>.
- [11] Y. Yang, X. Lu, J. Jiang, J. Ma, G. Liu, Y. Cao, W. Liu, J. Li, S. Pang, X. Kong, C. Luo, Degradation of sulfamethoxazole by UV, UV/H₂O₂ and UV/persulfate (PDS): Formation of oxidation products and effect of bicarbonate, *Water Res.* 118 (2017) 196–207, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2017.03.054>.
- [12] A. Javadi, S. Latif, M. Imran, N. Hussain, M. Bilal, H.M.N. Iqbal, MXene-based hybrid composites as photocatalyst for the mitigation of pharmaceuticals, *Chemosphere* 291 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.133062>.
- [13] Y. Yi, X. Chen, Y. Zhao, X. Xu, P. Zhang, C. Li, MXene-Based Semiconductor Materials for Various Applications in Photocatalysis Field, *Energ. Technol.* 13 (2025), <https://doi.org/10.1002/ente.202301520>.
- [14] N.H. Solangi, R.R. Karri, S.A. Mazari, N.M. Mubarak, A.S. Jatoti, G. Malafaia, A. K. Azad, MXene as emerging material for photocatalytic degradation of environmental pollutants, *Coord. Chem. Rev.* 477 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccr.2022.214965>.
- [15] G. Murali, J.K. Reddy Modigunta, Y.H. Park, J.H. Lee, J. Rawal, S.Y. Lee, I. In, S. J. Park, A review on MXene synthesis, stability, and photocatalytic applications, *ACS Nano* 16 (2022) 13370–13429, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.2c04750>.
- [16] M.-H. Tran, Q.T.H. Ta, D.T.Y. Oanh, N.H. Hieu, J.-S. Noh, Electrochemical catalysis and photocatalysis in nanomaterials: a review, *Vietnam J. Chem.* n/a (n.d.), doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/vjch.70120>.
- [17] N. My Tran, Q. Thanh Hoai Ta, J.S. Noh, Unusual synthesis of safflower-shaped TiO₂/Ti₃C₂ heterostructures initiated from two-dimensional Ti₃C₂ MXene, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 538 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2020.148023>.
- [18] M. Alhabeb, K. Maleski, B. Anasori, P. Lelyukh, L. Clark, S. Sin, Y. Gogotsi, Guidelines for Synthesis and Processing of Two-Dimensional Titanium Carbide (Ti₃C₂T_x MXene), *Chem. Mater.* 29 (2017) 7633–7644, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.7b02847>.
- [19] E. Boorboor Azimi, A. Badieli, M. Hossaini Sadr, A. Amiri, A template-free method to synthesize porous G-C₃N₄ with efficient visible light photodegradation of organic pollutants in water, *Adv. Powder Technol.* 29 (2018) 2785–2791, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apt.2018.07.027>.
- [20] Z. Jin, X. Jiang, Q. Zhang, S. Huang, L. Zhang, L. Huang, T. He, H. Zhang, T. Ohno, S. Ruan, Y.J. Zeng, Infrared response in photocatalytic polymeric carbon nitride for water splitting via an upconversion mechanism, *Commun. Mater.* 1 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43246-020-00093-z>.
- [21] F. Brette, S. Célérier, C. Canaff, L. Loupias, M. Paris, A. Habriou, F. Boucher, V. Mauchamp, XPS Binding Energy Shifts in 2D Ti₃C₂T_x MXene go largely Beyond Intuitive Explanations: Rationalization from DFT Simulations and Experiments, *Small Methods* 9 (2025) 2400848, <https://doi.org/10.1002/smt.202400848>.
- [22] A.V. Vähätalo, R.G. Wetzel, H.W. Paerl, Light absorption by phytoplankton and chromophoric dissolved organic matter in the drainage basin and estuary of the Neuse River, North Carolina (U.S.A.), *Freshw. Biol.* 50 (2005) 477–493, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2427.2004.01335.x>.
- [23] United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), Ecological Structure Activity Relationships (ECOSAR) Predictive Model, (n.d.), <https://www.epa.gov/tsca-screening-tools/ecological-structure-activity-relationships-ecosar-predictive-model> (accessed November 27, 2024).
- [24] R.T. Wright, K. Fay, A. Kennedy, K. Mayo-Bean, K. Moran-Bruce, W. Meylan, P. Ranslow, M. Lock, J. Vince Nabholz, J. Von Runnen, L.M. Cassidy, J. Tunkel, Methodology Document for the Ecological Structure-Activity Relationship Model (ECOSAR), 2022.
- [25] M.S. Alam, M.A. Chowdhury, M.A. Kowser, M.S. Islam, M.M. Islam, T. Khandaker, Advances of MAX phases: Synthesis, characterizations and challenges, *Eng. Rep.* 6 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1002/eng.212911>.
- [26] T. Cai, L. Wang, Y. Liu, S. Zhang, W. Dong, H. Chen, X. Yi, J. Yuan, X. Xia, C. Liu, S. Luo, Ag₃PO₄/Ti₃C₂ MXene interface materials as a Schottky catalyst with enhanced photocatalytic activities and anti-photocorrosion performance, *Appl. Catal. B* 239 (2018) 545–554, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2018.08.053>.
- [27] H. Wang, Y. Wu, T. Xiao, X. Yuan, G. Zeng, W. Tu, S. Wu, H.Y. Lee, Y.Z. Tan, J. W. Chew, Formation of quasi-core-shell In₂S₃/anatase TiO₂/metallic Ti₃C₂T_x hybrids with favorable charge transfer channels for excellent visible-light-photocatalytic performance, *Appl. Catal. B* 233 (2018) 213–225, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2018.04.012>.
- [28] V.Q. Hieu, T.K. Phung, T.Q. Nguyen, A. Khan, V.D. Doan, V.A. Tran, V.T. Le, Photocatalytic degradation of methyl orange dye by Ti₃C₂-TiO₂ heterojunction under solar light, *Chemosphere* 276 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.130154>.
- [29] E. Cerrato, C. Gionco, M.C. Paganini, E. Giamello, E. Albanese, G. Pacchioni, Origin of Visible Light Photoactivity of the CeO₂/ZnO Heterojunction, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* 1 (2018) 4247–4260, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaem.8b00887>.
- [30] V.R. Ananda, F.N. Ramadhan, A.M. Kautsari, T. Amrillah, A. Hermawan, Y. Yulizar, J. Gunlazuardi, T. Sekino, S. ichi Orimo, S. Yin, Powder engineering of MXene-based heterojunction materials for photocatalysis and gas sensor applications, *Adv. Powder Technol.* 36 (2025), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apt.2025.104789>.
- [31] P. Eghbali, A. Hassani, S. Wactawek, K.Y. Andrew Lin, Z. Sayyar, F. Ghanbari, Recent advances in design and engineering of MXene-based catalysts for photocatalysis and persulfate-based advanced oxidation processes: A state-of-the-art review, *Chem. Eng. J.* 480 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2023.147920>.
- [32] Q.T.H. Ta, A. Sreedhar, N.N. Tri, J.S. Noh, In situ growth of TiO₂ on Ti₃C₂T_x MXene for improved gas-sensing performance, *Ceram. Int.* 50 (2024) 27227–27236, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2024.05.020>.
- [33] Z. Dessoliers, A. Chemin, G. Valurouthe, R. Lord, T. Bilyk, Y. Gogotsi, V. Mauchamp, T. Petit, Combining x-ray photoelectron and absorption spectroscopies for determining surface chemistry and composition of Ti₃C₂T_x MXene, *Adv. Mater. Interfaces* 12 (2025), <https://doi.org/10.1002/admi.202500391>.
- [34] J. Halim, K.M. Cook, M. Naguib, P. Eklund, Y. Gogotsi, J. Rosen, M.W. Barsoum, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy of select multi-layered transition metal carbides (MXenes), *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 362 (2016) 406–417, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2015.11.089>.
- [35] V. Natu, M. Benchakar, C. Canaff, A. Habriou, S. Célérier, M.W. Barsoum, A critical analysis of the X-ray photoelectron spectra of Ti₃C₂T_x MXenes, *Matter* 4 (2021) 1224–1251, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matt.2021.01.015>.
- [36] S. Karamat, R.S. Rawat, P. Lee, T.L. Tan, R.V. Ramanujan, Structural, elemental, optical and magnetic study of Fe doped ZnO and impurity phase formation, *Prog. Nat. Sci.: Mater. Int.* 24 (2014) 142–149, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnsc.2014.03.009>.
- [37] R.A. Vazirov, S.Y. Sokovnin, V.G. Ilves, I.N. Bazhukova, N. Pizurova, M. V. Kuznetsov, Physicochemical characterization and antioxidant properties of cerium oxide nanoparticles, in: J. Institute of Physics Publishing, *Phys. Conf. Ser.* 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1115/3/032094>.
- [38] L.Ä. Näslund, M.H. Mikkilä, E. Kokkonen, M. Magnuson, Chemical bonding of termination species in 2D carbides investigated through valence band UPS/XPS of Ti₃C₂T_x MXene, *2D Mater.* 8 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1088/2053-1583/ac1ea9>.
- [39] J.R. Zhang, Y. Ma, S.Y. Wang, J. Ding, B. Gao, E. Kan, W. Hua, Accurate K-edge X-ray photoelectron and absorption spectra of g-C₃N₄ nanosheets by first-principles simulations and reinterpretations, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 21 (2019) 22819–22830, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9cp04573b>.
- [40] M.M. Khan, N.H. Saadah, M.E. Khan, M.H. Harunsani, A.L. Tan, M.H. Cho, Phytogenic Synthesis of Band Gap-Narrowed ZnO Nanoparticles Using the Bulb Extract of *Costus woodsonii*, *Bionanoscience* 9 (2019) 334–344, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12668-019-00616-0>.
- [41] M.N. Tran, M. Moreau, A. Addad, A. Teurtrie, T. Roland, V. de Waele, M. Dewitte, L. Thomas, G. Levéque, C. Dong, P. Simon, K. Ben Tayeb, D. Mele, V. Ordonsky, B. Granddier, Boosting Gas-Phase TiO₂ Photocatalysis with Weak Electric Field Strengths of Volt/Centimeter, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 16 (2024) 14852–14863, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaami.3c19031>.
- [42] Q.T.H. Ta, M.H. Tran, T.M.H. Nguyen, P.K.T. Nguyen, D.H. Nguyen, Engineering heterojunction noble metal (NM)@ZnO catalyst for improved CH₄ photocatalytic oxidation, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.* 170 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inoche.2024.113345>.
- [43] K. Saravanakumar, K. Yun, V. Mahes Kumar, Y. Yea, G. Jagan, C.M. Park, Construction of novel In₂S₃/Ti₃C₂ MXene quantum dots/SmFeO₃ Z-scheme

- heterojunctions for efficient photocatalytic removal of sulfamethoxazole and 4-chlorophenol: Degradation pathways and mechanism insights, *Chem. Eng. J.* 451 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.138933>.
- [44] T. Ke, S. Shen, K. Yang, D. Lin, In situ fabrication of Bi₂O₃/C₃N₄/TiO₂@C photocatalysts for visible-light photodegradation of sulfamethoxazole in water, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 580 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2021.152302>.
- [45] S. Atri, E. Loni, F. Zazimal, K. Hensel, M. Caplovicova, G. Plesch, X. Lu, R. Nagarajan, M. Naguib, O. Monfort, MXene-Derived Oxide Nanoheterostructures for Photocatalytic Sulfamethoxazole Degradation, *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* 7 (2024) 16506–16515, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsanm.4c02523>.
- [46] H. Liang, J. Guo, M. Yu, Y. Zhou, R. Zhan, C. Liu, J. Niu, Porous loofah-sponge-like ternary heterojunction g-C₃N₄/Bi₂WO₆/MoS₂ for highly efficient photocatalytic degradation of sulfamethoxazole under visible-light irradiation, *Chemosphere* 279 (2021) 130552, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHEMOSPHERE.2021.130552>.
- [47] S. Shen, T. Ke, D. Fang, D. Lin, N and S co-doping of TiO₂@C derived from in situ oxidation of Ti₃C₂ MXene for efficient persulfate activation and sulfamethoxazole degradation under visible light, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 297 (2022) 121460, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SEPPUR.2022.121460>.
- [48] H. Zhang, Z. Wang, R. Li, J. Guo, Y. Li, J. Zhu, X. Xie, TiO₂ supported on reed straw biochar as an adsorptive and photocatalytic composite for the efficient degradation of sulfamethoxazole in aqueous matrices, *Chemosphere* 185 (2017) 351–360, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHEMOSPHERE.2017.07.025>.
- [49] A. Hernández-Zanoletty, O. Cabezuelo, A. Paris-Reche, I. Oller, M.I. Polo-López, A. Agüera, P. Plaza, M.L. Marín, F. Boscá, S. Malato, Assessment of new immobilized photocatalysts based on TiO₂ for wastewater decontamination, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 11 (2023) 111291, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JECE.2023.111291>.
- [50] H. Gong, W. Chu, H. Gong, A. Huang, J. Lin, M. Yan, Cooperation of Fe(II) and peroxymonosulfate for enhancement of sulfamethoxazole photodegradation: mechanism study and toxicity elimination, *RSC Adv.* 10 (2020) 35646–35657, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0RA05704E>.
- [51] P. Reuschenbach, M. Silvani, M. Dammann, D. Warnecke, T. Knacker, ECOSAR model performance with a large test set of industrial chemicals, *Chemosphere* 71 (2008) 1986–1995, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHEMOSPHERE.2007.12.006>.
- [52] UNECE, Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals (GHS). <https://unece.org/ghs-rev8-2019>, 2019 accessed November 27, 2024.
- [53] M. Majewsky, D. Wagner, M. Delay, S. Bräse, V. Yargeau, H. Horn, Antibacterial activity of sulfamethoxazole transformation products (TPs): general relevance for sulfonamide TPs modified at the para position, *Chem. Res. Toxicol.* 27 (2014) 1821–1828, https://doi.org/10.1021/TX500267X/SUPPL_FILE/TX500267X_SI_001.PDF.